

ASPRIN TABLETS' MATRIX FORMS: FORMULATION, EVALUATION AND COMPARATIVE PREFORMULATION STUDY USING VARIOUS NATURAL POLYMERS

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ABSTRACT

The present study was to formulate Aspirin matrix tablet using Xanthan gum, and guar gum as natural polymers and to elucidate the effect of type of polymers and its concentration on release pattern of drug from sustained release matrix tablets. Aspirin matrix tablets were prepared in four batches (batch number F1 to F4) by direct compression method using xanthan gum and guar gum as natural polymers and microcrystalline cellulose as a binder and pyrolidone as a water soluble polymer. The in vitro drug release studies of all the batches indicated that optimized formulation pertaining to Batch no. F2 was a promising system to provide sustained release effect of drug. The release pattern of the above formulation was best fitted to zero-order model and first order model. Mechanism of drug release followed was non-Fickian (super case-II) transport mechanism. Based on the above studies it can be concluded that this Azithromycin drug can be effectively formulated using

different classes of natural polymers which can have greater bioavailability with less dose related side effects having better patient compliance.

KEYWORDS: Aspirin, Guar gum, Xanthan gum, microcrystalline cellulose, Pyrolidone, Talc.

INTRODUCTION

Drug delivery is the method or process of administering a pharmaceutical compound to achieve a therapeutic effect in humans or animals.^[1,2] Drug delivery technologies modify drug release profile, absorption, distribution and elimination for the benefit of improving product efficacy and safety, as well as patient convenience and compliance. Drug release is from: diffusion, degradation, swelling, and affinity-based mechanisms.^[3] Most common routes of administration include the preferred non-invasive peroral (through the mouth), topical (skin), transmucosal (nasal, buccal/sublingual, vaginal, ocular and rectal) and inhalation routes.^[4,5] Many drugs, peptide and protein, antibody, vaccine and gene based, in general may not be delivered using these routes because they might be susceptible to enzymatic degradation or cannot be absorbed into the systemic circulation efficiently due to molecular size and charge issues to be therapeutically effective. For this reason many protein and peptide drugs have to be delivered by injection or a nano-needle array. To achieve and maintain the concentration of administered drug within the therapeutically effective range needed for a medication, it is often necessary to administer conventional dosage forms several times a day. These results in rise of drug level after each administration with subsequent fall which results in fluctuated drug level.^[20,29,25] The concept of sustained release was introduced in the early 1950s and the first patent on sustained release was obtained by Israel Lipowski who worked on coated pellets. There has been more than 50 years of research and development on sustained release dosage forms to prolong drug levels in the body.^[17,21,23] Successful fabrication of sustained release product is usually very difficult and involves consideration of physico-chemical parameters and pharmacokinetic behavior of drug, route of administration, disease state to be treated and, most important placement of the drug in the dosage form that will provide the desired temporal and spatial delivery pattern for the drug. Types of sustained release formulations include liposome's, drug loaded biodegradable microspheres and drug polymer conjugates. Basically there are three basic modes of drug delivery, i.e. targeted delivery, controlled release and modulated release.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Materials Aspirin was gift sample by Medico Remedies Pvt. Ltd. Juhu, Mumbai. Guar gum, Xanthan gum was procured by Merck Specialties private Limited., India. Talc, Magnesium stearate was purchased from Apex Chemicals, Ahmadabad, India. Microcrystalline cellulose (MCC) Polyvinyl pyrrolidone was purchased from Loba chemie Private Ltd. Mumbai.

Method

Method for preparation matrix tablet of Aspirin

The controlled release matrix tablets of aspirin were prepared by the direct compression method. The drug, polymers and other excipients were passed through sieve # 80. The controlled release tablets containing drug, matrix materials, diluents, binder and lubricants were mixed uniformly and compressed on 10 station tablet machine using 8 mm round and flat punches with hardness between 5-7 kg cm⁻².

Table 1: Formulation trials of 250 mg aspirin matrix tablets.

Formulation Code	Drug (mg)	Xanthan gum (mg)	Guar gum (mg)	MCC	PVP	Talc	Magnesium Stearate	Total
F1	250	125	-	189	30	6	-	600
F2	250	-	125	189	30	6	-	600
F3	250	250	-	64	30	-	6	600
F4	250	-	250	64	30	-	6	600

Each formulation contains 10 tablets.

Table 2: Micromeritic properties of formulation blends.

Formulation Code	Angle of Repose	Bulk Density	Tapped Density	Hausner's Ratio	Carr's Index
F1	24.03 ± 0.78	0.425 ± 0.03	0.512 ± 0.017	1.20 ± 0.03	16.99 ± 2.25
F2	26.61 ± 0.98	0.467 ± 0.1	0.551 ± 0.1	1.17 ± 0.02	15.24 ± 1.68
F3	28.24 ± 0.86	0.438 ± 0.06	0.510 ± 0.08	1.16 ± 0.01	14.11 ± 0.88
F4	29.55 ± 1.09	0.495 ± 0.09	0.590 ± 0.04	1.19 ± 0.01	16.10 ± 1.15

The obtained micromeritic properties are given in Table no.2. The value of Angle of repose of formulation within the range of 30°, indicating good flow properties for the granules. The tapped density values ranged between 0.510 ± 0.08 to 0.608 ± 0.04 g/ cm³ and the bulk density values ranged between 0.425 ± 0.03 to 0.516 ± 0.07 g/ cm³. The result of Carr's Index range from 14.09 ± 0.86 to 17.69 ± 1.95% suggests good flow characteristics of the granules. Hausner's Ratio range from 1.16 ± 0.01 to 1.21 ± 0.09% which indicates good flow property of microspheres.

Table 3: Physico-chemical properties of matrix tablets of aspirin.

Formulation Code	Thickness (\pm S.D) (mm)	Hardness (\pm S.D) (kg/cm ²)	Friability (\pm S.D) (%)	Weight variation (\pm S.D) (%)	Percentage Content (\pm S.D) (%)
F1	0.574 \pm 0.054	6.73 \pm 0.16	0.45 \pm 0.01	\pm 2	99.79 \pm 0.36
F2	0.596 \pm 0.070	6.79 \pm 0.28	0.35 \pm 0.07	\pm 1	99.96 \pm 0.23
F3	0.579 \pm 0.83	6.79 \pm 0.20	0.39 \pm 0.08	\pm 2	99.95 \pm 0.51
F4	0.592 \pm 0.53	6.77 \pm 0.28	0.43 \pm 0.02	\pm 1	99.74 \pm 0.56

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Preformulation Studies

1. Standard Calibration Curve

The λ_{\max} was found at 276 nm in 0.1 N HCl, and phosphate buffer (P^H-6.8) and The standard calibration curve for Aspirin with regression value of 0.984 and 0.994 are shown in figure 1 and 2 respectively. The relation between drug concentration and absorbance is linear and the curve obeys Beer-lamberts law within the concentration range of 5 to 25 μ g/ml of Aspirin.

2. Differential Scanning Calorimetry Thermogram

The supplied gift sample was identified by DSC thermogram. Identification of the drug can be described from the fig.8-10.

3. Drug Polymer Interaction Studies

This FTIR spectrum confirms the identity of pure aspirin based on the following signature peaks: Ester carbonyl (C=O) stretch at \sim 1805 cm^{-1} – strong and sharp. Carboxylic acid C=O stretch \sim 1750 cm^{-1} . Aromatic ring vibrations between \sim 1600–1450 cm^{-1} . C–O and O–H stretching in the region 1250–1000 cm^{-1} as shown in Fig no.5-6. The FTIR spectrum confirms the presence of all key components: Aspirin: Identified by strong ester (C=O at \sim 1748 cm^{-1}), aromatic ring stretches (1605, 1482, 703 cm^{-1}). Xanthan gum & Guar gum: Show broad –OH stretch (\sim 3650 cm^{-1}), C–O–C (ether) stretches (\sim 1000–1200 cm^{-1}), and complex fingerprint region signals. No major unexpected peaks, indicating no significant interaction or degradation among components.

Fig. 1: Standard curve of aspirin in phosphate buffer 0.1N HCl (P^H 1.2).

Fig. 2: Standard curve of Aspirin in phosphate buffer (P^H 6.8).

Fig. 3: FTIR spectra of Aspirin.

Fig. 4: FTIR spectra of Aspirin & Polymers.

Fig. 5: Release Data to be fitted in Zero order Release Kinetics for Formulations F1.

Fig. 6: Release Data to be fitted in Zero order Release Kinetics for Formulations F2.

Fig. 7: Data to be fitted in Zero order Release Kinetics for Formulations F3.

Fig. 8: Data to be fitted in Zero order Release Kinetics for Formulations F4.

Fig. 12: Release Data to be Fitted in Fitted in First order Kinetics for Formulations F1.

Fig. 13: Release Data to be Fitted in Fitted in First order Kinetics for Formulations F2.

Fig. 14: Release Data to be Fitted in Fitted in First order Kinetics for Formulations F3

Fig. 15: Release Data to be Fitted in Fitted in First order Kinetics for Formulations F4.

Fig. 15: Release Data to be fitted in Fitted in Higuchi Release for Formulations F1.

Fig. 16: Release Data to be Fitted in Fitted in Higuchi Release for Formulations F2.

Fig. 16: Release Data to be Fitted in Fitted in Higuchi Release for Formulations F3.

Fig. 17: Release Data to be Fitted in Fitted in Higuchi Release for Formulations F4.

Statistical Evaluation of Release Data

Table 4: Release Kinetics profiles of matrix tablets of aspirin.

Formulations	Zero Order Model		1 st Order Model		H-M Model	
	R ²	K ₀	R ²	K ₁	R ²	K _h
F1	0.955	4.35	0.731	0.208	0.947	11.88
F2	0.975	4.74	0.954	0.206	0.950	14.33
F3	0.952	4.43	0.920	0.207	0.934	12.02
F4	0.956	4.57	0.796	0.106	0.912	10.02

DISCUSSION

In the present study, sustained release matrix tablets of Aspirin were successfully formulated, developed, and evaluated using natural polymers, Xanthan Gum, and Guar Gum. These natural polysaccharides are inexpensive, biodegradable, and possess excellent hydrophilic and swelling properties, which make them effective in controlling drug release. From the dissolution profile study of Four formulations of Aspirin formulations namely: **F1, F2, F3 & F4**, it was found that the **F2** formulations release profile best predicted by Zero order release kinetics named found to be the best released with R² value of **0.975**, which is nearer to **0.999**. The properties and the viscous nature of the Xanthan gum retards release of the drug from the dosage form. This natural polymer is also appealing for use in drug delivery for a wide range of molecular weights, varying chemical compositions, low toxicity and biodegradability. The matrix tablets of Xanthan gum are given sustained release pattern of drugs from tablets. So it can be concluded from the above experiment that between Four formulations **F2** shows best release profile in our laboratory atmosphere and set up.

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